

THE BRITISH INSTITUTE OF PERSIAN STUDIES

مؤسسه ایرانشناسی بریتانیا

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تلفن : ۸۲۰۳۱۷
تهران

238, Ave. Takhte Jamshid.
Tel: 820317
Teheran

27. 276 -

Dear Andrew,

Thanks for your letter and
the copies of papers enclosed -

I did not raise your
questions with Naumi when I last
saw him since I can do so on
Aug 14th just before Quinis begins,
and I was pressing for the Quinis
permit at the time - (Have just
heard the High Council approved the
Quinis application; they turned down
everything else including ^{the} Japanese
& de Otiroshadgi.)

I shall write to Fabra & seal

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اخبار و اطلاعیه‌ها

a telegram to the Hotel Naz for
good measure the latter will
be discreet viz. "one is fine
also rest" or whatever.

(You name Simaf as one;
Hormay as two, & B Chahak as three.)

in haste,

Yours,

David